

Influence of specular factor on heat transport in nanoribbons of different sizes

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In this paper, the phonon heat transfer in two-dimensional conductors with different types of phonon reflection from the boundaries is examined. Heat conductors with arbitrary ratios of width W to length L are studied assuming that the mean free path between phonon-phonon collisions is infinite. The integral equations for the angular distribution functions of the incident and reflected phonons at a specific point on the conductor boundary were proposed. To solve these integral equations a new iterative method is proposed. The proposed iterative approach formally corresponds to taking into account subsequent collisions of phonons with the edges of the conductor. It ensures the convergence of the desired solution for any W/L ratio and for any value of the specular coefficient p . Interpolation formulae are found to describe with sufficient accuracy the solution of the system of integral equations in the entire region of the specular coefficient p from 0 to 1, and the W/L ratios ranging from 10 to 0.01. These formulae allow the construction of the isolines of the thermal conductance coefficient values, from which it is possible to determine the necessary values of W/L and parameter p to get the desired value of the thermal conductance.

Keywords: nanoribbon, phonon, heat conductance, specular reflection, diffusive reflection, iterations.

Introduction

The dependency of heat transfer efficiency in 2D nanoribbons was studied in detail in [1, 2] as a function of the width W and the length L for the case of purely diffuse phonon reflection from the wall boundaries. In the diffuse reflection limit, phonons are reflected from the boundary isotropically in all directions and therefore produce maximum thermal resistance [3]. This occurs because the maximum number of phonons is reflected back with respect to the direction of the incident phonon. In the reverse limit reflection at boundaries is fully specular. In this case, backward reflection is in principle impossible, because the phonon momentum component directed along the reflecting boundary does not change.

The actual reflection of a phonon from a non-ideally smooth wall can be described as some kind of superposition of these two limiting cases. In the simplest model by

Ziman [4], the concept of the probability of specularity of reflection p is introduced where p is equal to unity for the absolutely specular reflection and zero for the opposite diffuse limit.

A generalization of the models from Refs. 3, 4 to the case of cylindrical heat conductors of finite length was carried out in Refs. 5, 6. Moreover, in these works an external temperature gradient was not specified on the lateral surfaces of the conductor, but a finite temperature difference only at the ends of the conductor was imposed. To solve this problem, integral equations were proposed that made it possible to consider different values of the specular coefficient p . In those studies, the results obtained by numerical methods were presented for a limited range of conductor lengths. This limitation was primarily caused by the slow convergence of their iterative methods.

In this work, we use the standard iterative method [1] which we generalize to the case of two integral equations

of incident and reflected phonons. The main advantage of this method is the fact that each of successive iteration corresponds to the next interaction of phonons with the boundary. This made it possible to track both the number of phonon reflections and their travel lengths. The second advantage of the method is its monotonic convergence despite the huge number of iterations that are necessary to consider the case of very long conductors [7].

Model of the system

To describe the phonon system in two-dimensional samples, we introduce the concept of distribution functions of incident phonons f_{inc} and reflected phonons f_{spec} . The relation between them in the case of specular reflection is given by the following relation:

$$f_{spec}(k_x, k_y) = f_{inc}(k_x, -k_y). \quad (1)$$

Here, the vector $\mathbf{k} = (k_x, k_y)$ is the phonon wave vector. In this case, the x axis is taken along the boundary of the sample, and the y axis is chosen perpendicularly to the boundary.

For the case of purely diffuse reflection, it is assumed that the distribution of reflected phonons is completely isotropic, that is, all reflection angles are equally probable. Hence,

$$\begin{aligned} f_{diff}(k_x, k_y) &= f_{diff}(k \cos \varphi, k \sin \varphi) = f_{diff}(k, \varphi) \\ &= \frac{1}{2} \eta(0 \leq \varphi \leq \pi) \int_0^\pi f_{inc}(k, \tilde{\varphi}) \sin \tilde{\varphi} d\tilde{\varphi}. \end{aligned} \quad (2)$$

Here, k is the length of the wave vector, and the angle φ is measured from the positive direction of x axes (it is the angle between the boundary and direction of phonon motion). The function $\eta(0 \leq \varphi \leq \pi)$ (so-called unitary rectangle function) describes the uniform distribution of reflected phonons over the entire range of angles from 0 to π . In the variables k and φ , relation (1) takes the form

$$f_{spec}(k, \varphi) = f_{inc}(k, \varphi). \quad (3)$$

According to the Ziman model [4], the distribution function of reflected phonons in the intermediate case has the form

$$f_{refl}(k, \varphi) = p f_{spec}(k, \varphi) + (1-p) f_{diff}(k, \varphi). \quad (4)$$

In our study, we consider nanoribbons with arbitrary ratios of width W to length L . A stationary heater ensures a constant temperature on one side, and a cooling thermostat constitutes a cold reservoir on the other side (see Fig. 1). A stationary heat flow thus occurs in the heat conductor. The magnitude of this flow is determined both by the dimensions of the nanoribbon, the physical properties of its edges, and, more precisely, by the nature of the interaction of heat carriers, i.e., phonons, with the edges.

Fig. 1. The geometry of the problem.

The system of equations

In our formulation, we introduce the incident $F_{inc}(z, \varphi)$ and reflected $F_{ref}(z, \varphi)$ heat fluxes at the lateral boundaries, which are the functions of the coordinates and direction, and obtain the system of integral equations for these functions from the Eqs. (1)–(4). The first of these equations [Eq. (5)] describes the angular distribution of incident phonons at each point on the boundary:

$$\begin{aligned} F_{inc}(x, \varphi) &= g(x, \varphi) + F_{ref}(x - W \operatorname{ctg} \varphi, \varphi) \\ &\times \eta(0 < x - W \operatorname{ctg} \varphi < L). \end{aligned} \quad (5)$$

Here, $g(x, \varphi)$ is the phonon flux that moves directly from all points of the heater to a definite point on the boundary having the coordinate x :

$$g(x, \varphi) = \frac{1}{W} \Theta \left(\frac{W}{\sqrt{W^2 + x^2}} - \sin \varphi \right), \quad (6)$$

where $\Theta(x)$ is the Heaviside unity step function.

The second term in Eq. (5) refers to phonons that move to the point of coordinate x on the boundary from a point on the opposite wall with the coordinate $x - W \operatorname{ctg} \varphi$. This term describes the free motion of phonons between two successive interactions with the walls.

The second integral equation describes the reflection law of phonons (4):

$$\begin{aligned} F_{ref}(z, \varphi) &= p F_{inc}(z, \varphi) + \frac{1}{2} (1-p) \eta(\pi - \varphi) \\ &\times \int_0^\pi F_{inc}(z, \tilde{\varphi}) \sin \tilde{\varphi} d\tilde{\varphi}, \end{aligned} \quad (7)$$

where p is the factor (probability) of specular reflection.

Similar equations are derived in the works of [5, 6] for cylindrical conductors. In those studies, the results obtained by numerical methods were presented for a limited range of conductor lengths. This limitation was primarily caused by the slow convergence of their iterative methods. In this work, we use the standard iterative method [1] which we generalize to the case of a system of Eqs. (5), (7). The main advantage of this method is the fact that each of successive iteration corresponds to the next interaction of phonons with the boundary. This made it possible to track both the number of phonon reflections and their travel lengths.

Iterative solution

As an initial approximation, we take the phonons arriving at the side boundary directly from the heater to be

$$F_{\text{inc}}^{(0)}(x, \varphi) = g(x, \varphi). \quad (8)$$

After reflection, the distribution function of these phonons, according to (7) has the form

$$F_{\text{ref}}^{(0)}(x, \varphi) = pF_{\text{inc}}^{(0)}(x, \varphi) + \frac{1}{2}(1-p)\eta(\pi - \varphi) \times \int_0^\pi F_{\text{inc}}^{(0)}(x, \tilde{\varphi}) \sin \tilde{\varphi} d\tilde{\varphi} \quad (9)$$

and is taken as an initial approximation for the reflected function.

Each successive approximation for the incident phonon distribution function is determined by the following recursive relation that is determined by the second term in Eq. (5):

$$F_{\text{inc}}^{(n+1)}(x, \varphi) = F_{\text{ref}}^{(n)}(x - W \operatorname{ctg} \varphi, \varphi) \times \eta(0 < x - W \operatorname{ctg} \varphi < L). \quad (10)$$

This relationship describes phonons that arrive at a given point on the boundary from the opposite wall and had previously made exactly n collisions with the walls.

The respective approximation for the reflected phonon distribution function is again determined by the distribution function of the incident phonons from Eq. (7):

$$F_{\text{ref}}^{(n+1)}(x, \varphi) = pF_{\text{inc}}^{(n+1)}(x, \varphi) + \frac{1}{2}(1-p)\eta(\pi - \varphi) \times \int_0^\pi F_{\text{inc}}^{(n+1)}(x, \tilde{\varphi}) \sin \tilde{\varphi} d\tilde{\varphi}. \quad (11)$$

In each iteration step, one can determine the complete distribution function

$$F_{\text{inc}}^{(N)}(x, \varphi) = \sum_{n=0}^N F_{\text{inc}}^{(n)}(x, \varphi) \quad (12)$$

and the heat flux by integrating over angles

$$G^{(N)}(x) = \int_0^\pi F_{\text{inc}}^{(N)}(x, \varphi) \sin \varphi d\varphi. \quad (13)$$

It should be noted that other methods of iterative solution of the integral system of Eqs. (5) and (7) are also possible. In particular, we can exclude one of the desired distribution functions from the system and solve the resulting equation for the other function. The disadvantages of this method are that the expressions for the inhomogeneous term and the kernel of such an integral equation are more complex compared to the functions included in Eqs. (5) and (7).

Another technique was used in the pioneering works of Perlmutter *et al.* [5] and Klitsner *et al.* [6]. In those works, the two-step iterative solution method was proposed. In the first step, an intermediate integral equation was derived, in which the kernel and inhomogeneous term were determined by preliminary iterations. Such a procedure, as shown in Ref. 6, ensures convergence of the results only for a limited range of values of the specularity coefficient p and conductor length L .

The solution method proposed in our work provides stable and monotonic convergence for any values of the specularity coefficient and any length of the conductor. In addition, it has the feature that allows us to accumulate the result of successive iterations and, if necessary, continue to improve the result.

We emphasize that our method is, in addition to being a purely mathematical algorithm, also portrays a certain physical meaning. Indeed, each iteration corresponds to the subsequent collision of a phonon with a wall. This fact makes it possible to determine, as in Ref. 1, various physical parameters, for example, the phonon path lengths, travel times, trajectories, etc.

Results for the profile of energy flux

In order to discuss our results, we introduce the function $t(x)$ that characterizes the phonon density [1, 6]. In fact, $t(x)$ is a normalized parameter that determines the particle flux density at a given point of the conductor boundary with the longitudinal coordinate x . It is equal to unity at the source of particles ($x = 0$) and equal to zero at the sink ($x = L$).

$$t(x = 0) = 1 \quad \text{and} \quad t(x = L) = 0. \quad (14)$$

Also, for convenience, we normalize (or choose such units of measurement) the heat flux, so that it is equal to unity in the heater. Consequently, we have the following relation between value of $t(x)$ and heat flux $G(x)$:

$$t(x) = WG(x). \quad (15)$$

Now, to test the robustness of our iteration processes, we consider the cases of different W/L ratios at different p values.

Let us consider at first the limiting cases for which the physics is obvious. In the case of absolutely specular reflection only, we should obtain the expected physical results, when normalized heat flux the inside the conductor is constant and is equals to the average between the normalized temperatures of the heater and the cooler that is

$$t(0 < x < L) = \frac{1}{2}. \quad (16)$$

Such an obvious result allows us to test the convergence of the numerical method for solving the integral Eqs. (5) and (7). The results of such testing for the absolutely spe-

Fig. 2. (Color online) The coordinate dependencies of the energy flux profiles for different number of iterations. The figures demonstrate the convergence of the numerical method for solving the system of integral Eqs. (5), (7) for W/L : 0.01 (a), (c), (e); 0.1 (b); 0.05 (f); 0.08 (d), and for different values of the specularity factor p . Lines respond to different number of iterations.

cular case ($p = 1$) are presented in Figs. 2(a) and 2(b). One can see that for a long conductor, the number of iterations is really huge, but the fact that the correct, albeit obvious result (16) is achieved in this case indicates a satisfactory monotonic convergence of the method.

The physical picture of the obtained results is fairly obvious. The value 1/2 indicates that all phonons that arrive from the right at a given point have undergone a definite

number of purely specular reflections after leaving the heater. In this case, the large number of iterations indicates that a large number of such specular reflections are necessary for the phonons to reach a given point of the conductor.

For this reason, the expected $t(x)$ value of 1/2 near the heater is formed almost “instantaneously” in two or three iterations. On the other hand, the final $t(x)$ profile near the cold end is formed after a much larger number of iterations.

For the same reason, it is obvious that the number of iterations required for convergence increases significantly with the conductor length.

In Figs. 2(c) and 2(d), we present typical results for the opposite limiting case $p = 0$. These results are typical for the very wide interval $0 \leq p < 0.9$. The figures show that $t(x)$ a profile quickly forms at the ends of the conductor, and then this profile stabilizes rather slowly in the middle of the conductor. The number of iterations required to form final profile in the middle of the conductor again increases with the length of the conductor.

This picture of the formation of energy flux profile $t(x)$ is very similar to the formation of temperature according to the usual Fourier law when unequal temperatures are set at the ends of the conductor. This similarity is due to the presence of diffuse reflection, which formally models the diffusion stochastic dissipative propagation of heat according to the law of thermal conductivity (Fourier law).

Here, it is necessary to note the significant difference between the case under consideration and Fourier's law. This refers to the presence of a temperature jump at the boundaries of the conductor due to the free movement of phonons emitted by the heater before their first reflection from the walls of the conductor. At the cold end, the same jump is due to the movement of phonons after the last reflection from the wall before hitting the cold end. These processes also determine the difference from the strict linearity of the coordinate dependence of temperature discussed in Ref. 1.

Figures 2(e) and 2(f) demonstrate typical results for the case, when the value of p is very close to unity but not equal to it, that is, $1 > p > 0.99$. These figures show that for this case, the energy flux profile is formed both at the ends of the conductor and in the middle of the conductor for the same number of iterations. This situation occurs at a very low degree of diffuseness and is typical for fairly long wires and has been discussed in detail in Ref. 7.

For W/L ratios greater than 1, the behavior of the iteration procedure has the same behavior as for the case $W/L < 1$ but differs only in the number of iterations that must be done to obtain a solution for a given required accuracy.

To demonstrate convergence, in Figs. 2(c)–2(e) and 2(f) (p is not equal to 1), we present two lines with a large number of iterations: red and blue (highest number of iterations), which clearly demonstrate convergence of the iteration process.

Our iterative algorithm allows the identification of domains characterized by the specular parameter p and the W/L ratios that determine the formation of different temperature profiles. For not very long conductors with $W/L \geq 0.1$, the iteration procedure is quite monotonous and is similar to the situation of a purely diffuse solution [1]. The only exception is in the case of almost fully specular reflection when $p \geq 0.995$.

The behavior of phonons within very long conductors is quite different. In this case, it turns out that adding very little backscattering leads to a sharp increase in the thermal resistance. This issue was discussed in detail in a previous report by the authors [7]. This feature is caused by the need for a phonon to undergo a very large number of reflections from the boundary walls until it reaches the cold end. This amount is of the order of several thousands, therefore, even for a specularity value of $p = 0.995$, the probability of at least one diffuse backscattering is quite high. In Fig. 2(f) one can see that even for a long conductor with $W/L = 0.05$, the probability of diffuse reflection $1 - p = 0.007$ provides a noticeable slope of the temperature profile, and, thus, a noticeable thermal resistance.

It is also worth noting that, both from the figures and from the physics of the scattering processes of phonons within a conductor, there is a similarity in the dependence of heat fluxes on the parameter p and on the W/L ratio. For example, when p tends to unity, the energy flux tends to a constant value, independent of the W/L ratio (horizontal). A similar behavior is obtained when W/L tends to infinity (very short conductors). Also, in the opposite limiting case when p tends to zero, all temperature profiles obviously coincide with the results for the purely diffuse limit, obtained, for example, in Refs. 1, 2. We therefore introduce a universal combination of $W/(1 - p)$ which replaces W in the presence of diffuse. The resulting dependencies can now be used to describe intermediate cases.

In the fully diffusive phonon regime [1], we should get an almost linear energy flux, with a maximum difference between temperatures at the ends of the sample. Such a linear dependence is often found for an approximated description of rarified gas motion in the Knudsen regime [8] inside a tube with finite length [9, 10]. As for nanoribbons or 2D conductors, the analogous solution for the energy flux was used in [2]:

$$t_{\text{app}}(z) = \frac{1}{2} + \Delta T_{\text{app}}(W, L) \left[\frac{1}{2} - \frac{z}{L} \right], \quad (17)$$

where the difference $\Delta T(W, L)$ is defined from the Eq. (7) when $p = 0$:

$$\Delta T(W, L) = \left(1 + \frac{4W}{L} \frac{\sqrt{L^2 + W^2}}{L + W + \sqrt{L^2 + W^2}} \right)^{-1}. \quad (18)$$

As shown in Ref. 2, this linear approximation gives a relatively good description of the solution (see Fig. 3) and in this paper, it will be used for interpolation in the case $p = 0$.

For further discussions, it is necessary to consider the other integral thermal properties that characterize a given heat conductor, namely, heat flux and thermal conductance coefficient. The total heat flux passing through the conductor is determined by the relation

Fig. 3. The dependence on W/L ratio of difference $\Delta T(W, L)$ at the ends of the conductor for the case of diffuse reflection. Squares describe the solution of Eq. 7 for the case $p = 0$, line curve respects to analytical approximation (18).

$$Q(p, W, L) = 1 - \int_0^L dx \left[1 - \frac{x}{\sqrt{W^2 + x^2}} \right] G(x, p, W, L), \quad (19)$$

where the second term corresponds to the backflow of phonons to the heater due to reflection and is determined by the function $G(x)$ given by Eq. (13). Using the analytical approximation (17), the heat flux is found from relations (15), (17) and has the form

$$Q_{\text{diff_app}}(W/L) = Q(p=0, W, L) = \frac{W + \sqrt{L^2 + W^2}}{L + W + \sqrt{L^2 + W^2}} - \frac{\Delta T(W, L)}{2} \left\{ 1 - \frac{W}{L} \ln \left(\frac{L + \sqrt{L^2 + W^2}}{W} \right) \right\}. \quad (20)$$

As for the coefficient of thermal conductance, here we will consider a definition, in which the difference $\Delta T(W, L)$ is determined by the temperatures of the heater and cooler itself, and not by the temperatures near the ends inside the conductor. In this case, the normalized coefficient of thermal conductance is determined as

$$\kappa = \frac{Q}{t(0) - t(1)} \equiv Q. \quad (21)$$

So, it is equivalent to the heat flux. Consequently, the analytical approximation for conductance in the case of diffuse reflection can be written as

$$\kappa_{\text{diff}}(W/L) = Q_{\text{diff_app}}(W/L) = \frac{W + \sqrt{L^2 + W^2}}{L + W + \sqrt{L^2 + W^2}}. \quad (22)$$

Figure 4 shows the dependence of the thermal conductance on the degree of specular reflection for samples

Fig. 4. Heat flow (thermal conductance) dependencies on the specularly coefficient p for different W/L ratio indicated in the figure. Points are the results of numerical calculation. Lines represent the analytical interpolation given by Eq. (23).

of different widths and lengths. As an analytical interpolation, we propose to use the relation that is obtained from the analytical dependence for the completely diffuse case given by Eq. (22) and by replacing the argument W/L with the ratio $W/L/(1-p)$, which provides correct results in opposite limiting case:

$$\kappa(p, W, L) = \kappa_{\text{diff}} \left(\frac{W/L}{1-p} f(p, W/L) \right). \quad (23)$$

Here, a correction factor is $f(p, w)$ used to account for the dependency at intermediate values of p :

$$f(p, w) = 1 + \frac{p}{1+aw} (b + (1-p)). \quad (24)$$

The fitting values a and b are determined from comparison with the results of numerical calculations. When minimizing the absolute standard deviation, the values $a = 4$ and $b = 0.45$ were obtained, for which the absolute deviation reached is 0.6%. The relative standard deviation reached a minimum value of 3% with parameters $a = 9$ and $b = 0.7$. Figure 5 shows the dependency of the thermal conductivity coefficient on the W/L ratio for various values of the specularly coefficient p . The figures demonstrate a fairly good agreement between the analytical interpolation formula (23) and the numerical solution of the integral equations.

For the case of not very long conductors, it turns out that it is possible to use another interpolation, which is a linear combination of the results for the limiting cases of specular reflection and diffuse reflection (22) given as

$$\kappa(p, W, L) = (1-p) \kappa_{\text{diff}}(W/L) + p(1-p) \kappa_{\text{diff_spec}}(p, W/L) + p \kappa_{\text{spec}}(p). \quad (25)$$

Fig. 5. Thermal conductance dependencies on the width to length W/L ratio for different p . Points are the results of numerical calculation. Lines represent the analytical interpolation given by Eq. (23) for different values of p indicated in the figure.

Here, $\kappa_{\text{diff_spec}}(p, W)$ is the fitting interpolation expression that best describes for intermediate values for p :

$$\kappa_{\text{diff_spec}}(p, w) = \frac{1}{1.25 + 5w} + \frac{1}{1-p} \left(\exp\left(\frac{p-1}{0.05 + 3.5w}\right) - 1 \right). \quad (26)$$

The disadvantage of this interpolation is the large number of parameters and the restricted range of applicability limited to $W/L > 0.1$.

The analytical formula (23) makes it possible to construct isolines of constant values of the thermal conductance on the coordinate system $p - W/L$.

Figure 6 allows the selection of suitable W/L parameter with a known degree of roughness in order to get the desired value of the thermal conductance. Or, on the contrary, using the known values of the conductivity coefficient and the dimensions of the sample, it is possible to determine the degree of specularity.

Fig. 6. Heat flux (thermal conductance) isolines in coordinates $p - W/L$.

Conclusion

This paper considers the problem of heat transfer by phonons in two-dimensional conductors of different width W to length L ratios and different degrees of specularity of reflection from the boundaries of the conductor in the approximation of the absence of interaction between phonons. Integral equations are derived for the angular distribution functions of phonons as a function of coordinates.

The iterative technique for solving such systems, which formally corresponds to taking into account subsequent collisions of phonons with walls is demonstrated. This approach ensures convergence of the proposed methods for any relationship between the length and width of the conductor and for any values of the specularity coefficient p .

An analytical interpolation formula is proposed that describes with sufficient accuracy the solution of the system of integral equations in the entire considered region for the specularity coefficient ranging from 0 to 1 and for the width to the length ratios ranging from 10 to 0.01.

Isolines of the thermal conductivity coefficient values have been constructed from which it is possible to determine values of W/L and p parameters corresponding to a given value of the thermal conductance.

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Вплив фактора дзеркальності
на теплоперенесення в нанострічках
різного розміру

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Досліджено фононний теплообмін у двовимірних провідниках з різними типами відбиття фононів від границь. Теплопровідні матеріали з довільним відношенням ширини W до довжини L досліджуються в припущенні, що довжина вільного пробігу між фонон-фононними

зіткненнями є нескінченною. Запропоновано інтегральні рівняння для кутових функцій розподілу падаючих і відбитих фононів у певній точці межі провідника. Для розв'язання цих інтегральних рівнянь запропоновано новий ітераційний метод. Представлений ітераційний підхід формально відповідає врахуванню наступних зіткнень фононів з краями провідника. Він забезпечує збіжність шуканого розв'язку для будь-якого співвідношення W/L і для будь-якого значення коефіцієнта дзеркальності p . Знайдено інтерполяційні формули, які з достатньою точністю описують розв'язок системи інтегральних рівнянь у всій області коефіцієнта дзеркальності p від 0 до 1 та відношень W/L від 10 до 0,01. Ці формули дозволяють побудувати ізолінії значень коефіцієнта теплопровідності, з яких можна визначити необхідні значення W/L і параметра p для отримання бажаного значення коефіцієнта теплопровідності.

Ключові слова: нанострічка, фонон, теплопровідність, дзеркальне відбиття, дифузійне відбиття, ітерації.